

SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISING AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The study was aimed at analysing the impact of social media advertisement on consumer buying behaviour. The survey research was used in this study to sample the opinion of respondents. This method involved random selection of respondent who were administered with questionnaires. The target population of the study comprised of students of selected departments in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The questionnaire administered was one hundred and ten (110) copies and one hundred copies retrieved which constitute the sample size. The descriptive and analytical approach was adopted using Chi-square to test and analyze the hypotheses earlier stated. The findings revealed that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products and that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. It was therefore concluded from the findings that social media reach allows consumers to create content in line with the firm's products and services. This study concludes that social media mix allows the firm to use a combination of various communication channels in targeting different market segments and its main objective is to help the businesses in meeting up with the various marketing objectives. It was recommended that Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries should embrace the use of social media reach in targeting different market segments to effectively influence consumer buying behaviour.

Keywords: Social Media, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Buying Behaviour

Introduction

The emergence of Web 2.0, one of the most significant developments in the history of commerce, was followed by the emergence of social media as an evolution based on Web 2.0. This technological revolution had a significant impact on traditional marketing approaches, ushering in a new era among marketers, an era in which social media changed completely the relationships between marketers and stakeholders, social media is shifting the power from all users as customers will now be in touch with one another, sharing information about goods and services, which requires advertisers to adapt their old tactics to match the current needs of consumers, to contact them as personally as possible., especially in their buying behavior by using social media as marketing channel in both free as word-of-mouth and paid as social media advertising. Furthermore, advertising is simply one way that consumers learn about new products, learn about things consumers may want or need, because the more consumers know about products more choices they can make, as no one prefer to make poor choices when

it comes to purchase, what social media provide is smart many choices more than poor or just many choices (Evans, 2018).

Thus, consumer's buying behavior is often influenced by a leading brand. This value is created by generating demand (via repurchases) and securing of future earnings for the organization (Sullivan and Oliveira, 2013). Therefore, social media marketing serves as opportunities for communication and depends upon new and unusual thought patterns (Kweskin, 2018). This helps customer's product and brand experience. This new era of digital communication and social engagement is preeminent for strategizing in business. Therefore, as organizations are becoming more competitive globally, it is pertinent for them to explore marketing strategy in a more compelling and innovative way so as to attract larger number of customers (Rockendorf, 2011).

Social media is at its core human communication, possessing characteristics of participation, openness, conversation, community and connectedness (Veil, Buehner and Palenchar, 2011). It is these characteristics of social media that enable an individual to communicate with other people across geographical boundaries about a service, product, an organization or any other thing for that matter. Social media is distinguished from traditional media in ways such as reach, frequency, accessibility, immediacy and many more. Due to these intrinsic features of social media, modern advertisers often prefer them to the traditional media. According to Pookulangara and Koesler (2011), social media enables 25% of all customers to post links about products, services information in their retail sites to update other users about the purchase process. Some examples of social media are blogs, wikis, social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Google+ and many more. Advertising on the other hand is "any form of personal presentation and promotion of goods, services, or ideas by an identified sponsor" (Kotler, 2010). It is a process of communication between a seller or a producer and a buyer that eventually results in an action by the buyer, be it to purchase, to use or to dispose a product or service. Advertising is one thing that can be admired or otherwise disliked due to its aesthetic value or the message it carries but that cannot be ignored due to its intriguing nature. Due to the evolution of many businesses, advertising also has evolved similarly and taken many different forms such as social media advertising to tackle and match the changes in businesses. Advertising is in a state of change due to growth of digital technology, online communication, consumers accustomed to the commercial environment and increase in clutter (Springer, 2017). Advertising, coupled with social media with respect to the exciting and interactive features of the latter, gives advertisers a much wider range of audiences who are virtually connected, making its impact quick and contagious.

Social media advertising has gained the preference of many organizations due to its interactive nature coupled with the relatively easy evaluation of advertising efforts on these platforms (Webster and Hume, 2015). These social media platforms to name a few, Facebook, Snapchat and Twitter have enabled the customer to access more

information and also to have a more direct involvement in organization that advertise on these platforms. The use of influencers in social media advertisements has made the effects of social media advertising even greater and to an extent, making consumers buy products they do not even have need of (Rishi, 2018). The mass communication channel most widely used in advertising, particularly in the case of consumer products, television is also the advertising support that has experienced the fastest expansion and which has the greatest impact on consumer's behaviour (Jefkins, 2010). Looking over to Television advertisement, its essence has not become obsolete by the influx of social media advertising as it combines visuals and audio in sending messages, quite similar to what is done in social media advertising. It however has some disadvantages of being very costly, and being perishable (forgotten if not repeated), it has some advantages of being targeted in cases where adverts are aired during some particular television shows as it would immediately reach the segment of the market that watch the show, and being able to reach a high audience as TV addresses a mass audience, homogeneous or heterogeneous (Bedore, 2012). Television adverts are good to reach a large audience nevertheless can be ignored by just a button on a remote control. The existence of many television channels has given customers a wide range of exposures and as such can easily miss or ignore adverts. Whereas this is a problem to television advertising, social media advertising is not left out as it has the tendency of becoming annoying especially in the case of pop-up advertisement on websites. Due to these handicapping limitations, there is a gap in knowledge as to which one is more effective: Television advertising or social media advertising. Inasmuch as social media are great advertising platforms as they offer easy, fast and real-time involvement with organizations, their inherent dangers to society cannot be underrated. One must own an account on social media before experiencing the advertising benefits that come with these platforms. Possessing these accounts make one vulnerable to several threats like internet addiction and Facebook depression, which is an emotional disturbance associated with Facebook usage when a user, typically a teenager is made to feel inferior to his or her counterparts on social media as they desire to be as they see them on social media which may not even be the case in reality (Trigger, 2018). Another of the threats is cyber bullying where false or embarrassing information are communicated to a specific user, driving that user to depression, anxiety, low self-esteem and in extreme cases even suicide. Many others also spend so much time on social media which results in loss of jobs and negligence to family and other aspects of their lives. These inherent evils of social media give them an unfavourable perception among some people in our societies, making social media a problem rather than a blessing. Therefore, this study seeks to determine whether the use of social media has an effect on the buying behaviour of Oral B and MYMY toothpaste consumers based on these enumerated issues.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify various social media advertising platforms.
2. To ascertain the link between the perception of customers about social media as advertising platforms.
3. To ascertain the perception of consumers about the use of social media advertising and their purchase intentions.
4. To examine how consumer trust has effect on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of consumers using Oral B and Mymy Toothpaste.
5. To examine how social media advertising has influenced the consumer buying behaviour of consumers using oral B and Mymy Toothpaste.
6. To examine the relationship between trust and purchase intention of consumers using Oral B and Mymy Toothpaste

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.
2. There is no significant relationship between trust and consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products

2.0 Review of Related Literature Conceptual Framework Concept of Social Media

Social media can be defined as “a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content” (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Moreover, Social Media Advertising can be defined as “An online Ad that incorporates user interactions that the consumer has agree to display and be shared. The resulting Ad displays these interactions along with the user’s persons (picture and/or name) within the Ad content” (IAB, 2009).

The concept of social media is a relatively new area of research. Social media has been defined by various scholars as a remote form of communication between individuals. In addition, it can be described as the blending of technology and social interaction for the co-creation of value (Bhanot, 2012). However, there is no evidence of a single, universal definition of the term since each discipline defines social media in the context of its own field. The most profound and agreed-upon definition of social media was posited by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010): “a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content.” Howard and Parks (2012) described social media in greater detail, dividing their definition into three sections:

- (1) The information infrastructure and tools used to produce and distribute content;

- (2) the content that takes the digital form of personal messages, news, ideas, and cultural products;
- (3) the people, organizations, and industries that produce and consume digital content (Howard, Philip, & Parks, 2019).

Social media has also been defined as “consumer-generated media that covers a wide variety of new sources of online information, created and used by consumers intent on sharing information with others regarding any topic of interest” (Kohli & Kapoor, 2014). The value of social platforms can be directly correlated with increasing internet usage and digitalization of social venues, with new generations being born into the world of social media (Putter, Akhunjonov and Obrenovic, 2017). Cibango argued that social media platforms have reformed every aspect of human behavior and societies worldwide, adjusting human needs in alignment with continuously evolving digital technologies (Cibango, 2013).

Concept of Consumer Buying Behaviour

Consumer buying behaviour refers to the methods involved when individuals or groups choose, buy, utilize or dispose of products, services, concepts or experiences to suit their needs and desires (Solomon, 1995). A behavior that consumers display in searching for, paying for, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they think will satisfy their needs (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2017). It is a convergence of three fields of social science, they are, individual psychology, societal psychology and cultural anthropology (Ramachander, 1988). A theory that answers what, why, how, when and where an individual makes purchase (Green, 2012); it is particularly important to study the subject of consumer buying behaviour as it facilitates firms to plan and execute superior business strategies (Khaniwale, 2015). In previous studies certain variables were found to have an impact in consumers. Companies are more concerned on individual consumer behavior as it helps them to yield information about how the consumers think, feel and choose their products. Every individual is a consumer. Consumer behaviour is the study of the process involved when individual or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of the product, service, ideas or experiences to satisfy needs and desires (Michael R.Solomon, 1998). The expand view of consumer embrace much more than the study of why and what consumer buy, but also focuses on how marketers influence consumers and how consumers use the products and services. The American Marketing Association also defines consumer behaviour as “the dynamic interaction of affect and cognition, behaviour and environmental events by which human beings conduct the exchange aspect of their lives” and describes how individual consumers, consumer groups and society at large constantly change and evolve. The dynamic nature of consumer behaviour implies that, one should not expect the same marketing strategy to work all of the time, or across all products, markets and industries. Schiffman & Kanuk (1997) define consumer behaviour as: "The behavior that consumers display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products,

services, and ideas." Schiffman & Kanuk (1997) elaborate on the definition by explaining that consumer behaviour is, therefore, the study of how individuals make decisions to spend their available resources (time, money, effort) on consumption-related items. It includes the study of what, why, when, where and how often they purchase and how they use the purchased product. In addition, it encompasses all the behaviours that consumers display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they expect will satisfy their needs. From a marketing perspective, consumer behaviour most probably became an important field of study with the development of the so-called marketing concept. Assael (1995) emphasises the influence of the marketing concept in marketing by stating that, according to the marketing concept, marketers first need to define benefits sought by consumers in the marketplace, followed by the drafting of marketing plans supporting the needs of consumers.

Social Media and Consumer Buying Behavior

Kaplan & Haenlein, (2010), depict web-based social networking as a group of web put together applications that work with respect to the ideological and technological establishment of web and permit the creation and exchange of client produced content in this way, social media makes clients a platform to meet up on the web and exchange, talk about, impart and take an interest in any type of social association which can include messages, audio, pictures, recordings and other media exclusively or mix. Firms must be aware that social media tools such as user profiles, customer ratings and reviews are trending towards becoming the source of information for any customer when they are making an important purchase (Ngai, Moon, &

Tao, 2012). The Internet has forced almost every facet of our business and daily lives to change. The way customers and business come together is shifting away from the traditional model and this evolution is just beginning (Mishra & Ayatham, 2017). The rise of the Internet has an important impact on word-of-mouth communication. Instead of having just your neighbors (Enyinda, Ogbuehi, & Mbah, 2018) or friends to chat with you, you can now access the entire world with just a few clicks. In traditional word-of-mouth communication, we rely on people we know and trust. This familiarity is often not present on the Internet. Also, in an online environment sender and receiver of information are separated by both space and time, whereas in its offline equivalent, people need to be together to communicate (Baird & Parasnis, 2011). The improvement of online networking has not gone unnoticed by the business circle. Numerous organizations keep up their own Facebook page and plan their commercials with the expectation that they will become a web sensation (Atkin, 2012). Making and observing one's own image discussion has been a training embraced by supervisors for quite a while. Bloggers are frequently sponsored in return for endorsements. According to Hosanagar (2013), Twitter has become an increasingly important source of communication for many companies. Altogether, eMarketer.com

evaluated 2010 overall informal organization publicizing spending at USD 3.3 billion, contrasted with USD 2.53 billion out of 2009. However, for the tremendous totals of cash being spent via web-based networking media advertising, there is still a lot of weakness among experts about the best promoting practices in this new field. The encounters of Sony, Wall-Mart and Nestlé are saddening instances of that (Hoyer, 2010). Duncan (2013) in his study on social media tool he revealed that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site. Most brand exposures on Facebook occur through users' news a feed, comScore said, rather than visit to dedicated brand pages on Facebook. Consumers who click a button that they like a certain brand or product tend to outspend others for that particular brand, comScore said, citing examples such as Amazon, Best Buy, and Target. Purchase data comes via information from loyalty clubs, credit card companies, and third-party collectors, with the permission of the study participant (Marino & Prestti, 2018). Organizations have responsibilities to decide overall objectives, sub goals, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and to make a decision on which specific channels should be used for which goals and which audiences (Pesonen, 2013). This process requires comprehensive user target group research. The marketer (organization or individual) needs to be knowledgeable which target group's needs will be met by which corresponding channels and what these groups are in need of. Failure to do this may result in focusing on for example; Instagram channel while the target audience is on interest (Pongpaew, Speece, & Tiangsoongnern, 2017). The authors express those users an organization targets on social media may differ across channels, and even differ from the official corporate website. This aspect is affected (determined) by the organization's business goals and where the target groups are. Many institutions are mainly concerned in integrating social media into the business structures of their organization structures but do not have the know-how of what social media entails. Such organizations may also not have tangible channels to ascertain the inherent gains (Hoyer, 2010).

Facebook: In the case of Target, Facebook and comScore studied two groups. One group, made up of fans of Target and their friends, saw "earned" messages about Target updates about Target that run in news feeds and the like (Marino & Prestti, 2018). The second group was made up of Facebook users who weren't fans of Target and saw no messages. Both groups had identical purchase behavior at Target prior to the study. After the four-week study, the fans who saw the messages were 19% more likely to buy goods at Target than the group that didn't see the messages, and their friends were 27% more likely. To measure the impact of paid advertising, ComScore conducted a similar study involving a national retailer. It looked at groups of Facebook users who were exposed to a paid online Facebook campaign about that brand, and a test group that was not. Again, the two groups had identical purchase behavior before the study. By the fourth week of the study, the group that saw the messages

was 16% more likely to buy goods at the retailer than the group that did not see the messages (Campbell, Ferraro, & Sands, 2014). Separately, Facebook said it had conducted research on about 60 campaigns to measure their return on investment, or how many dollars in sales were generated by every dollar spent on Facebook advertising. About 70% of campaigns showed a return of three times or more on the money spent for the advertising, a spokeswoman said. About half of campaigns showed a return of five times or better (Helal, Ozuem, & Lancaster, 2018). Evaluating the effectiveness of advertising has proved challenging for Madison Avenue, no matter the media, brands have long said. They find it hard to gauge how many people saw a particular ad, and connecting the message with purchases is even more difficult (Marino & Prestti, 2018).

Twitter: Twitter being a social network and news enabling people to share and connect is perceived as a very different form of eWOM than any other social media platform. The research carried by UA Magazine shows that this is because of the unsolicited, tie strength and swiftness characteristics of the micro blog. Whereas most studies focused on consumers that were actually looking for information prior to a purchase, on Twitter consumers are exposed to an unsolicited form of eWOM (Enyinda, Ogbuehi, & Mbah, 2018). The user may just bump into a tweet about a product or brand. This means that the level of involvement is much lower than on a product review website. Also, the quality of the review may differ from a traditional review website. For example, a high-quality message is more logical and persuasive and therefore more effective. Considering a tweet can only contain 140 characters, they tweet have to be to the point to have any effect (Duncan, 2013). According to Ngai (2012), people are using such social media through the web, texting messages through mobile phones (with internet Connection), or external applications. Such social media have become very popular now days to connect with people at large or people of the country and communicate instantly and effectively. Such new ways of communication are distinguished from that of traditional media in terms of more consumer engagement, exchange of information through many ways, messaging and tracking.

Instagram: Research shows that Instagram is the most effective social marketing tool, outpacing Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and celebrities when it comes to influencing consumers according to Japanese App Takumi which connects people with brands (Balci & Cetin, 2017). The study, commissioned by Japanese app Takumi, finds Instagram delivers more sales and consumer actions than other social platform. Facebook placed second in terms of social contenders, followed by YouTube and finally blogs which were found to be the least influential medium overall (Gummerus, Liljiander, & Pihlström, 2012). Chahine and Malhotra (2018), carried out a study on Instagram, the findings indicated that Millennials were found to be the most responsive group, with 68 per cent of 18-24 years old claimed they are more likely to buy something after someone they follow on Instagram

shared it. Just over a majority, 54 per cent of respondents said they bought products after spotting them on the channel.

YouTube: More than ever social media platforms are changing the way we live and do things. Social media has a strong impact and influence on customers. More importantly, brands are using up social platform to engage users as their customers. Brand advertising in social media is now the ground zero to build a bond between the customers and the brands (Hudson, 2013). In 2006 YouTube arrived at the spectacular video advertising platform for marketing brands. It not only honed creativity, but if the ad is good enough, it is shared, commented on and popularized it. In the Q2 2014 report of YouTube Insights, the bottom line was, brands that are hell-bent on identifying customer's passion are the ones who influenced more purchases than others who didn't. The report states that 66% of beauty product buyers were influenced by YouTube advertising to make purchases as they felt they could relate it to their lifestyle. This comes naturally when beauty conscious people are on the lookout for make-up and hairdo how tips on accessorizing and beauty expert advice videos. Brand advertising of beauty products on such user base is definitely attractive. Also, 62% of Smartphone buyers were reported to have been influenced by the Smartphone review videos on YouTube (Hoyer, 2010).

Theoretical Review Motion Effects Theory

A theory that can explain which of the three advertisement conditions on social media will lead to the most brand awareness is the motion effects theory (Sundar & Kalyanaraman, 2013). The motion effects theory states that individuals tend to have an innate preference for moving objects over static objects. This is because motion grabs our attention and induces arousal. This effect has also been seen within advertising, with studies showing that animated advertisements induce higher levels of arousal and higher memory of the advertising content (Diao & Sundar, 2013; Sundar & Kalyanaraman, 2013). This was also the case in Day, Shyi & Wang (2016) study on flash banners, which investigated whether flash banners were either distracters or that these types of banners induced arousal. The results showed that flash banners indeed led to arousal and also increased processing of the advertising content (Day et al., 2016). According to these studies, the more motion and animation used in an advertisement the higher the brand awareness (Day et al., 2016; Sundar & Kalyanaraman, 2013). Thus, when it comes to advertising on social media, the video content of story advertisements is likely to induce more arousal, as this content involves more motion compared to influencer marketing and photo advertisements which are static images.

Empirical Review

Delrue Laura (2017) studied the impact of Instagram 's social influencers on consumer attitude and purchase behaviour of lifestyle products on young Belgian women. The study aimed at understanding the impact of Social

Influencers through Instagram on the buying behaviour of lifestyle products of young Belgian women. The study took into account the various factors involved such as attitude, credibility, persuasion attempt and sponsorship disclosure of Influencer Marketing through Instagram. The study was conducted using a sample of around 425 women between the age group of 18-29 years. The paper also throws a light on the rising popularity of platforms like Instagram raises, which makes it an interesting platform for marketing ends. Also, Consumer purchase behaviour of young women is characterized by a high engagement, searching information online, and reviewing on social media about purchases. Furthermore, they are very sensitive to prices and digitally connect before purchasing. The research also suggests that small companies can use Instagram digital influencers to improve their reach and expand their target audience. But the selection of the interviewees for the study was not random and the outcomes of the qualitative and the quantitative research were not in line with the hypothesis drawn.

Chryssoula Chatzigeorgiou et.al (2017) modelled the impact of social media influencers on behavioural intentions of millennial (Generation X and Generation Y) using the target millennial population between the age group 19-33 years. The studies included giving respondents a structured questionnaire and were asked to think of their social media accounts and their attitudes when interacting in social media when responding. It became evident that the prominent way to reach out to millennial is via social media accounts. The study found out that rural businesses need to use the personal relationships they develop with their customers and expand these relationships on social media. It is also apparent that traditional marketing fails to apply to small rural businesses, whereas influencer marketing becomes a valuable asset for tourism. The proposed model connects the millennial with the image, fame and social media presence of these influencers and is and the way decision making of millennial is influenced by the influencer marketing.

Ali J. Al-Kandari et.al (2016) studied the influence of culture on Instagram use and for that the state of Kuwait presents an excellent case for exploring the influence of culture on Instagram use. The sample included about 539 university students from Kuwait who were enrolled in general education courses to guarantee a sample representing diverse body of students from different fields, who participated in a questionnaire that took about 10 minutes to fill out. This segment is chosen because it uses Instagram more often than other age groups. This study confirms that males are more likely than females to post their personal pictures on Instagram, more likely to disclose their personal information and more likely to have public accounts unlike females who are more likely to have private accounts than males. The difference between males and females were captured by conducting independent t-test procedures. The study also depicted that families are more likely to reject that their daughters to allow other stranger males to follow them. Having male followers may show a female who is a playful.

Such image is because “The misbehaviour by women is believed to do more damage to family honour than the misbehaviour of men”.

Harshini (2015) this study conducts an analysis of the existing theoretical contributions on Social Media Advertisements and buying intention of the consumers. The study highlights the fact of Social Media Advertisements and its impact on intention to buy, previous studies investigated about the impact of advertisements given through website towards consumer’s shopping behaviour. This study provides a cluster of consumer’s response towards Social Media Advertisements with reference to customer buying Intention.

Pietro et al., (2012) explore the extent of social media, particularly Face book, influence buying decision. They find happiness in using social media for buying decision. The study reveals about consumer’s suggestions and recommendations on merchandise on Face book, enjoyment in finding the information on brands and products, attitude in the usage of various tools provided by social media for the buying decision of products. The study also infers a good relationship between the views of consumer towards buying intention of customer and social media. Shu-Chuan Chu et al., (2013) in their analysis examines the social media user’s responses for social media advertising. Consumers who are using social media as a tool of advertising to interact with others and with the brand. Due to numerous users in the age group 18-35, who are using social media, the online luxury market experienced enormous growth. Brand consciousness and awareness has an impact on user’s view on social media advertising that affects their response towards social media advertising and affects buying intention.

3.0 Methodology

The research used descriptive survey design as the strategy or plan of action regarding events which upon implementation will enable the researcher to investigate the problem of this study. The study was designed in a systematic process of providing answer to the research questions and research objectives. The population of study will comprise of selected students using Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries. Simple random sampling method was employed owing to its effectiveness in eliminating biasness and that it offers a better representation of the population. As a result of the inability of the researcher to effectively study the whole firms under study, a representative number was chosen as the sample size population. One hundred (100) respondents from selected students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University using Oral B and MyMy toothpaste product from the entire population were used as the sample size. The sample size was calculated using the Taro Yamani scientific formula which is given as:
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

N is the Population **1** is the constant

e is the degree of error expected **n** is the sample size

$$n = \frac{133}{1 + 133 (0.05)^2}$$

$$\frac{133}{1 + 133 (0.0025)}$$

$$\frac{133}{1 + 0.3325}$$

$$\frac{133}{1.3325}$$

$$n = 100$$

Data for this study came from the primary and secondary data. The primary data was generated through the field survey using structured questionnaire as a major research instrument. The secondary data on the other hand were obtained from relevant literatures ranging from textbooks, journals, articles, periodicals, seminar paper dissertation. To ascertain the validity of the instrument, content validity was adopted.

The reliability of instrument was determined by a reliability test through the use of Cronbach's Alpha to check the consistency of the intended measure. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for most of the constructs in the pilot study had an acceptable level of internal consistency based on the suggestion of Nunnally and Bernstein (2014). To solidify the reliability of the instruments, a pilot study of 20 questionnaires was carried out to evaluate the internal consistency of the instruments, the results show 0.841, which shows that the questionnaire is reliable. The descriptive and quantitative statistical method of data analysis was used to analyze the study of this research. The descriptive involve the use of tables and frequency distribution. The quantitative approach employs the non-parametric statistics such as chi-square for hypothesis testing for relationship observed and expected variables on the data. The data was obtained from the respondents through the administration of questionnaires which was collated and analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS Version 20.0).

4.0 Data Analysis, Findings and Discussion Bio-Data of Respondents

The gender distribution of the respondents used for this study. 60 respondents which represent 60.0percent of the population are male while the remaining 40 respondents which represent 40.0 percent of the population are female.

The age grade of the respondents used for this study. 15 respondents which represent 15.0percent of the population are below 17 years.15 respondents which represent 15.0 percent of the population are between 18-

20years.40respondents which represent 40.0 percent of the population are between 21-30years.10respondents which represent 10.0 percent of the population are between 31-40years.10respondents which represent 10.0 percent of the population are between 41-50years while 10respondents which represent 10.0 percent of the population are over 50years.The marital status of respondents used for the survey 60 respondents representing 60.0percent of the population are single.30 respondents representing 30.0 percent of the population are married.5 respondents representing 5 percent of the population are divorced while 5 respondents representing 5 percent of the population are widowed.

Responses on Research Instruments

The responses of respondents that the level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent strongly agree that the level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high. 25 respondents representing 25.0 percent agree that the level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high. 5 respondents representing 5.0 percent were undecided. 10 respondents representing 10.0 percent disagree that the level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high while the remaining 10 of the respondents representing 10.0 percent strongly disagrees that the level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using Oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high.

The responses of respondents that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 40 respondents representing 40.0 percent strongly agree that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent agree that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site. 2percent were undecided. 3 respondents representing 3.0 percent disagrees that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 5 of the respondents representing 5 percent strongly disagrees that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 10 respondents representing 10.0 percent disagree that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products while the remaining 10 of the respondents representing 10.0 percent strongly disagrees that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

The responses of respondents that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 40 respondents representing 40.0 percent

strongly agree that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent agree that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products. 2 respondents representing 2 percent were undecided. 5 respondents representing 5.0 percent disagrees that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products while the remaining 3 of the respondents representing 3 percent strongly disagree that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

The responses of respondents that there is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of oral B and MyMy toothpaste. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent strongly agree that There is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of oral B and MyMy toothpaste. 30 respondents representing 30.0 percent agree that there is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of oral B and MyMy toothpaste. 5 respondents representing 5 percent were undecided. 10 respondents representing 10.0 percent disagrees that There is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of oral B and MyMy toothpaste while the remaining 5 of the respondents representing 5 percent strongly disagrees that there is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste.

The responses of respondents that social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers. 40 respondents representing 40.0 percent strongly agree that social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers. 30 respondents representing 30.0 percent agree that social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers. 15 respondents representing 15.0 percent were undecided. 10 respondents representing 10.0 percent disagrees that social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers while the remaining 5 of the respondents representing 5.0 percent strongly disagrees that social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers.

The responses of respondents that Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent strongly agree that Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers. 25 respondents

representing 25.0 percent agree that Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers. 5 respondents representing 5.0 percent were undecided. 10 respondents representing 10.0 percent disagree that Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers while the remaining 10 of the respondents representing 10.0 percent strongly disagrees that Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers.

The responses of respondents that social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries. 40 respondents representing 40.0 percent strongly agree that social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent agree that social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries. 2 respondents representing 2 percent were undecided. 5 respondents representing 5.0 percent disagrees that social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries while the remaining 3 of the respondents representing 3 percent strongly disagree that social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries.

The responses of respondents that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site. 40 respondents representing 40.0 percent strongly agree that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site. 50 respondents representing 50.0 percent agree that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site. 2 respondents representing 2 percent were undecided. 5 respondents representing 5.0 percent disagrees that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site while the remaining 3 of the respondents representing 3 percent strongly disagrees that marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site.

Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis 1

H₀: There is no significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products

H₁: There is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

Level of significance: 0.05

Decision rule: reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than the level of significance, accept the null hypothesis if otherwise

	There is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products
Chi-Square	105.520 ^a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 11 Test Statistics

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 25.0.

Conclusions based on decision rule:

Since the p-value= 0.000 is less than the level of significance (0.05), we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: There is no significant relationship between trust and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between trust and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

Level of significance: 0.05

Decision rule: reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than the level of significance, accept the null hypothesis if otherwise.

Correlations

	There is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products	There is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products
There is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste N products	Pearson Correlation = 0.853** Sig. (2-tailed) = .000 N = 100	Pearson Correlation = 0.853** Sig. (2-tailed) = .000 N = 100
There is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste N products	Pearson Correlation = 0.853** Sig. (2-tailed) = .000 N = 100	Pearson Correlation = 0.853** Sig. (2-tailed) = .000 N = 100

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion Based on the Correlation Table Above

The correlation coefficient $R = 0.853$ indicates a strong positive relationship. We therefore conclude that there is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of Oral B and MyMy toothpaste products.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

Findings from the study revealed the following

1. The level of awareness of social media advertising by consumers using oral B and MyMy toothpaste is high

2. There is a significant influence of social media advertising on consumers buying behaviour of oral B and My toothpaste products
3. There is a significant relationship between social media advertising and consumers buying behaviour of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products
4. There is a significant effect of consumer trust on purchase intensity and perceived usefulness of oral B and MyMy toothpaste
5. Social media advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers
6. Access to social media platforms is capable of creating awareness about needs not met hitherto by the consumers
7. Social media reach empowers the firm to characterize its target audience as well as the objective market in Oral B and My toothpaste industries
8. Marketing on Facebook influences consumer behavior and leads to increased purchases for the brands that leverage the social-networking site.

Conclusion

Looking over to how effective social media adverts are in influencing consumer buying behaviour, it can be concluded that although many consumers use social media platforms, they actually do so not to patronise adverts but for other reasons such as to make new friends and to maintain old ones. This makes social media adverts less effective in influencing consumer behaviour with respect to the patronage of oral B and MyMy toothpaste products as some consumers even consider these adverts as nuisance. It can therefore be concluded that social media reach allows consumers to create content in line with the firm's products and services. This study concludes that social media mix allows the firm to use a combination of various communication channels in targeting different market segments and its main objective is to help the businesses in meeting up with the various marketing objectives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made that,

1. Since many consumers find social media adverts not helpful due to reasons like credibility and convenience, advertisers should consider being very truthful in their adverts so as to eradicate all traces or hints of deception, which would then grant them credibility in the eyes of their target markets.

2. On the features of social media and their level of attractiveness, since many of the participants in this study were very much attracted by videos in social media adverts, advertisers should tailor their adverts to include more videos than pictures and text to ensure more reach and attraction
3. Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries should embrace the use of social media reach in targeting different market segments to effectively influence consumer buying behavior.
4. Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries should create a social media mix that allows the use of a combination of various communication channels in targeting different market segments with the purpose of helping the businesses in meeting up with the various marketing objectives.
5. Oral B and MyMy toothpaste industries should develop content on Facebook that is in line with their products' offerings to drive traffic on the site. They should use their Twitter to tap into corporate clients by driving interaction of their products as well as services that is offered. By posting various images and pictures of their products and services on Instagram, they influence consumers to initiate purchase.

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